

NOTES

Magneto-electrophoretic Study of Ions on Filter Paper

(Comparative study of some ligand fields)

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In the present work¹, an attempt is made to compare qualitatively the field strength of some common ligands. It is known that some ligands like CN⁻ give rise to weakly paramagnetic complexes even when the central metal ion is strongly paramagnetic. For example, Fe³⁺ is strongly paramagnetic as free ion but the complex K₃[Fe(CN)₆] is weakly paramagnetic. But the same ion is found to form strongly paramagnetic complex K₃[FeF₆] with F⁻ as ligand. Hence the behaviour of ligands are different in respect of the magnetic susceptibility of the complexes formed by them. In text books, this property of ligands has been explained in terms of the "ligand field strength" or the "spin-pairing capacity" of the ligand. In the present work the field-strengths of some more common ligands are qualitatively compared.

Apparatus and Chemicals :

An electromagnet of 15 kilogauss strength, an ammeter, a milliammeter, a voltmeter, two rheostats, platinum electrodes, thin glass plates, beakers, switches, etc.

Filter paper used for the purpose of electrophoresis was Whatman No. 1 grade. Along with other chemicals, reagent quality oxalic acid, disodium salt of EDTA, potassium cyanide, potassium chloride, Mohr's salt, hydrofluoric acid, potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide, etc, were used.

Experimental

The circuit is made as shown in the diagram. The electromagnet is connected in series with a switch, an ammeter, a rheostat ; and a voltmeter is connected in parallel to this. The electrophoresis set is run through a different circuit and the milliammeter and the rheostat are connected in series. In a previous experiment, the field strength of the magnet was calibrated against the current flowing and thus the field strength is known at the time of

experiment from the ammeter reading only. The field strength is made as desired by controlling the current through the ammeter with the help of the rheostat.

The electrophoresis set is run by a separate switch and the current flowing through the paper can be controlled by the rheostat. The current can be read on the milli-ammeter.

Whatman No. 1 filter paper is cut into 1 cm × 40 cm strips. In a single observation a single strip is used. The complex to be studied is spotted (.01 ml) on a marked zero-line on the strip in the form of a normal solution. The strip is then moistened with the carrier electrolyte (M/5 KCl) solution. The strip is then sandwiched between the thin glass plates and the zero-line of the strip (visible through the glass plate) is placed at the centre of the magnetic field. The ends of the strip are dipped into the beakers full of the electrolyte and provided with platinum electrodes which form the cells. After the run the strip is dried in air oven and then developed with a suitable reagent.

Some of the complexes, e.g., K₄[Fe(CN)₆], K₃[Fe(CN)₆] are available in reagent quality samples. The rest are prepared in the laboratory from reagent quality starting materials using standard methods of synthesis.

EXPERIMENTAL DATA :

Carrier electrolyte : M/5 KCl solution,
Time of migration : 15 minutes
Terminal voltage : 220 volt D.C.
Maximum field strength : 15 kilogauss at 1.4 amp.
Half field strength : 7.5 kilogauss at 0.6 amp.

Central metal ion	Ligand	Complex in	Distance of the central line in mm from origin		
			without field	with half field	with full field
Mn ²⁺	CN ⁻	[Mn(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	25	19	16
	EDTA	[Mn-EDTA] ²⁻	22	18	13
	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	[Mn(C ₂ O ₄) ₃] ⁴⁻	20	17	12
Fe ³⁺	CN ⁻	[Fe(CN) ₆] ³⁻	25	19	15
	EDTA	[Fe(EDTA)] ⁻	22	16	13
	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	[Fe(C ₂ O ₄) ₃] ³⁻	22	14	9
	F ⁻	[FeF ₆] ³⁻	32	18	12
Co ³⁺	CN ⁻	[Co(CN) ₆] ³⁻	22	18	15
	EDTA	[Co-EDTA] ⁻	22	17	12
	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	[Co(C ₂ O ₄) ₃] ³⁻	23	17	12
	F ⁻	[CoF ₆] ³⁻	28	20	14

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Circuit Diagram :

Discussion

In the above experiment, it is clear that the ligands are different in their capacity of "spin pairing" or producing low-spin complexes from high spin central metal ions. The central atoms Mn^{2+} (5 unpaired electrons, d^5), Fe^{3+} (5 unpaired electrons, d^5) and Co^{3+} (4 unpaired electrons d^6) are all highly paramagnetic ions. But the results of magnetoelectrophoresis show that all their cyano-complexes are weakly paramagnetic. Thus CN^- is a very strong-field ligand. On the other hand, the fluoro-complexes are highly paramagnetic. Hence F^- is a weak field ligand. From the nature of the curves obtained⁺⁺ by plotting the data from the Table, it is possible to write the ligands with respect to their ligand-field strength, the following sequence:-

In the graph, distance migrated is plotted against field strength, from the slope of the curve, the paramagnetism of the complex is indicated, i.e., greater the slope, more is the paramagnetism, i.e., less is the ligand field. So, the order of the ligand field will be the reverse of the slope.

Reference

1. H. G. MUKHERJEE and D. MAJUMDAR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, 277, 205.

Addition Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Haloacetates with Nitrogen Donors

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THIS is in continuation to our work on complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) carboxylates with pyridine type bases¹⁻³ and we wish to report now

preparation and characterisation of a number of complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) haloacetates with heterocyclic ligands pyridine (Py), 2-, 3- and 4-methylpyridine (2-, 3-, 4-MePy), quinoline(Q) and isoquinoline(IQ) with a view to investigate their structure.

Experimental

Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) haloacetates were generated in solution by the interaction of the appropriate haloacetic acid with an excess of the required basic metal carbonate in ethanol under reflux and filtering off the excess of the unreacted metal carbonate. However, dichloroacetates of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) were isolated as solid samples by concentration of the filtrate obtained as described above. The initial crude products were recrystallised from methanol and dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide. Their purity was established by metal analysis. Heterocyclic ligands were purified by fractional distillation over potassium hydroxide before use.

Preparation of Complexes : Complexes of mono- and trihaloacetates were prepared by the direct addition of the ligand in 1 : 2 molar ratio to the appropriate metal(II) haloacetate generated in ethanol. The reaction mixture on concentration and crystallisation invariably gave a solid crystalline product which was separated, washed with the appropriate solvent and dried in vacuum over phosphorous pentoxide.

Complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) dichloroacetates were prepared by mixing the reactants in 1 : 2 or 1 : 4 metal to ligand ratios in acetone medium and working up the reaction mixture as described above.

Cobalt and nickel were estimated gravimetrically as tetrapyridinedithiocynatocobalt(II) and bis(dimethylglyoximate)-nickel(II) respectively. Carbon and hydrogen contents of the samples were estimated in the micro-analytical laboratory of this department. Conductance measurements were carried on millimolar solutions in acetone using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge type CL 01/0,2A. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene. Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra were recorded in chloroform on Beckman-DB-Spectrophotometer over the range 28,500-12,500 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra were recorded in Nujol mulls on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer Model 621.

The analytical results, magnetic moments, conductivity and molecular weights wherever recorded are cited in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results show that the complexes formed are either of 1 : 2 or 1 : 4 stoichiometry.